

COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT FORMING SIMULATION: CONTINUOUS AND MESOSCOPIC APPROACHES

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1 Introduction

The approaches to model the forming of textile composite reinforcements belong to two main families that are related to the scale at which the analysis is made. The textile reinforcement is a set of yarns (and a set of fibres). The analysis of the deformation can be made considering and modelling each of these yarns (or fibres) and their interactions (contact with friction). In this case the approach is called discrete or mesoscopic. Of course the number of yarns is high and the interactions are complex. On the opposite, the continuous approaches consider a continuous medium juxtaposed with the fabric and the mechanical behaviour of which is equivalent to those of the textile reinforcement. This mechanical behaviour is complex because it concerns large strains and strong anisotropy. Furthermore, it strongly changes during the forming.

The present paper aims to present continuous and discrete approaches for thin (2D) composite reinforcements forming simulations. First a continuous approach is described within a membrane assumption. It is based on a hyperelastic model. Then simulations of woven fabric forming based on a discrete approach are presented. Finally a semi-discrete approach which is an intermediate method between continuous and discrete ones is presented. The advantages and drawback of the different approaches are discussed.

2 Hyperelastic model

At macroscopic level, a woven fabric can be seen as a continuous material with a very specific mechanical behaviour, including high anisotropy and the ability to exhibit very large shearing and bending deformations. Investigation at the macroscopic level is the most popular for reinforcement forming simulations, as it allows using finite elements codes with standard shell or membrane elements and does not ask the description of the internal textile material structure [1-4].

In the present approach [5] a potential is defined which aim to reproduce the non linear mechanical behaviour of textile composite reinforcements. The proposed potential is a function of the right Cauchy Green and structural tensor invariants defined from the fibre directions. This potential is based on the assumption that tensile and shear strain energies are uncoupled. It is the sum of three terms.

$$W = \overline{W}_1(I_1) + \overline{W}_2(I_2) + \overline{W}_s(I_{12}) \quad (1)$$

This assumption (tensile and shear strain energies are uncoupled) are made for sake of simplicity. The independence of tensile behaviour relatively to in plane shear has been shown experimentally [6]. The other hypotheses are probably less true, but there are very few data available on the couplings.

The structural tensors $\underline{\underline{L}}_{\alpha\beta}$ are defined from the two unit vectors in the warp and weft directions $\underline{\underline{f}}_{10}$ and $\underline{\underline{f}}_{20}$ in the reference configuration:

$$\underline{\underline{L}}_{\alpha\beta} = \underline{\underline{f}}_{\alpha 0} \otimes \underline{\underline{f}}_{\beta 0} \quad (2)$$

The two first terms \overline{W}_1 and \overline{W}_2 are the energies due to the tensions in the yarns. They are function of invariants I_1 and I_2 respectively, themselves depending on the right Cauchy Green strain tensor $\underline{\underline{C}} = \underline{\underline{F}}^T \cdot \underline{\underline{F}}$ and the structural tensors $\underline{\underline{L}}_{\alpha\alpha}$:

$$I_1 = \text{Tr}(\underline{\underline{C}} \cdot \underline{\underline{L}}_{11}) = \lambda_1^2$$

$$I_2 = \text{Tr}(\underline{\underline{C}} \cdot \underline{\underline{L}}_{22}) = \lambda_2^2 \quad (3)$$

λ_α is the deformed length of on initially unit fibre in the direction α . The third term \overline{W}_s is a function of the second mixed invariants of $\underline{\underline{C}}$.

$$I_{12} = \frac{1}{I_1 I_2} \text{Tr}(\underline{\underline{C}} \cdot \underline{\underline{L}}_{11} \cdot \underline{\underline{C}} \cdot \underline{\underline{L}}_{22}) = \cos^2 \theta \quad (4)$$

The second Piola Kirchhoff stress tensor is derived from this potential

$$\underline{\underline{S}} = 2 \left[\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial I_1} - \frac{I_{12}}{I_1} \frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial I_{12}} \right] \underline{\underline{L}}_{\equiv 11} + 2 \left[\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial I_2} - \frac{I_{12}}{I_2} \frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial I_{12}} \right] \underline{\underline{L}}_{\equiv 22} + 2 \left[\sqrt{\frac{I_{12}}{I_1 I_2}} \frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial I_{12}} \right] (\underline{\underline{L}}_{\equiv 12} + \underline{\underline{L}}_{\equiv 21}) \quad (5)$$

Fig.1. Deformed shape of an unbalanced fabric with an initial orientation of fibres 0°/90° (experimental shape (a); Simulation without shear rigidity (b); Simulation with shear rigidity (c))

In order to define the form of the potential two complementary assumptions are made taking into account the specific woven fabric behaviour and its deformation modes. The potential has to vanish in a stress free configuration. Polynomial functions of the invariants are considered in the present work. The global form of the proposed potential energy is given by:

$$W(\underline{\underline{C}}) = \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{1}{i+1} A_i (I_1^{i+1} - 1) + \sum_{j=0}^s \frac{1}{j+1} B_j (I_2^{j+1} - 1) + \sum_{k=1}^l \frac{1}{k} C_k I_{12}^k \quad (6)$$

To determine the constants A_i , B_j and C_k , three experimental tests are necessary: two tensile tests in the warp and weft directions and one in-plane pure shear test.

The proposed hyperelastic model is implemented in a user routine VUMAT of Abaqus/Explicit and it is applied to membrane elements. The simulation of a hemispherical punch forming process is performed in the case of a strongly unbalanced twill. The warp rigidity is 50 N/yarn and the weft rigidity is 0.2 N/yarn. The experimental results in terms of deformed shape are shown figure 1 (a) together with the results of the simulation figure 7 (b and c). The hyperelastic model is described in detail in [5]

3 Mesoscopic approach

Fig.2. Meso-modelling of a unit cell of a plain weave. (a) FE model for the analysis of the behaviour of the unit cell. 47214 Dof. (b) FE model for simulations of the whole composite reinforcement forming. 216 Dof.

In discrete modelling (also called meso-modelling in the case of textile material), the modelling does not directly concern the textile material but each fibre bundle. This one is modelled by elements simple enough to render the computation possible because it concerns the forming of the whole composite reinforcement and the number of yarns and contacts between these yarns is very large. The interactions between warp and weft directions are taken into account explicitly by considering contact behaviour

and relative motions between the yarns are possible [7, 8]. At the microscopic level, each fibre is satisfactorily described as a beam but this approach is time consuming. The main difficulty is the great number of contacts with friction that have to be taken into account, especially for a woven fabric. For this reason, although this approach is promising, only very small elements of the fabric have been modelled to date [9, 10]. An alternative possibility is to use a continuous behaviour for each yarn (meso-modelling).

Fig.3. Simulation of hemispherical forming test using the unit cell model of figure 2(b).

This implies that the fibrous nature of the yarn is taken into account in this model especially in order to have rigidities in bending and transverse compression very small in comparison to the tensile stiffness. In any case, a compromise must be found between a fine description (which will be expensive from the computation time point of view) and a model simple enough to compute the entire forming process. Figure 2(b) show the finite element model used for discrete simulations of forming processes (216 dof (degrees of freedom)). It is compared to another FE model of the unit cell used in [11] (Figure 2(a)) to analyze the local in plane shear of a plain weave unit cell (47214 dof). It cannot be considered (at least today) to use this last FE model to simulate the forming of a composite reinforcement that is made of several thousands of woven cells. In the simplified unit cell (Figure 2 (b)) each yarn is described by few shell elements and the contact friction and possible relative displacement of the yarns are considered. The bending stiffness is independent of the tensile one and very much reduced in comparison to the one given by plate theories. Figure 3 shows the results of a

hemispherical forming simulation based using the modelling shown Figure 2b of the woven material.

4 Semi discrete approach

This approach takes into account the difficulties to describe the textile material as a continuum in one hand (continuous approach) and the difficulties to model all the yarns and their contacts in the other hand (discrete approach). In this approach that is more or less intermediate, the textile composite reinforcement is seen as a set of a discrete number of unit woven cells submitted to membrane loadings (i.e. biaxial tension and in-plane shear) and bending (Figure 4) [12].

In any virtual displacement field $\underline{\eta}$ such as $\underline{\eta} = 0$ on the boundary with prescribed loads, the virtual work theorem relates the internal, exterior and acceleration virtual works:

$$W_{\text{ext}}(\underline{\eta}) - W_{\text{int}}(\underline{\eta}) = W_{\text{acc}}(\underline{\eta}) \quad (7)$$

with

$$W_{\text{int}}(\underline{\eta}) = W_{\text{int}}^t(\underline{\eta}) + W_{\text{int}}^s(\underline{\eta}) + W_{\text{int}}^b(\underline{\eta}) \quad (8)$$

$W_{\text{int}}^t(\underline{\eta})$, $W_{\text{int}}^s(\underline{\eta})$, $W_{\text{int}}^b(\underline{\eta})$ are the internal virtual works of biaxial tension, in-plane shear and bending respectively with:

$$W_{\text{int}}^t(\underline{\eta}) = \sum_{p=1}^{\text{ncell}} {}^p \epsilon_{11}(\underline{\eta}) {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \epsilon_{22}(\underline{\eta}) {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_2 \quad (9)$$

$$W_{\text{int}}^s(\underline{\eta}) = \sum_{p=1}^{\text{ncell}} {}^p \gamma(\underline{\eta}) {}^p M^s \quad (10)$$

$$W_{\text{int}}^b(\underline{\eta}) = \sum_{p=1}^{\text{ncell}} {}^p \chi_{11}(\underline{\eta}) {}^p M^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \chi_{22}(\underline{\eta}) {}^p M^{22} {}^p L_2 \quad (11)$$

where ncell is the number of woven cell. L_1 and L_2 are the length of unit woven cell in warp and weft directions. $\epsilon_{11}(\underline{\eta})$ and $\epsilon_{22}(\underline{\eta})$ are the virtual axial strains in the warp and weft directions. $\gamma(\underline{\eta})$ is the virtual angle between warp and weft directions. $\chi_{11}(\underline{\eta})$ and $\chi_{22}(\underline{\eta})$ are the virtual curvatures of warp and weft yarns. $\epsilon_{11}(\underline{\eta})$, $\epsilon_{22}(\underline{\eta})$, $\gamma(\underline{\eta})$, $\chi_{11}(\underline{\eta})$ and $\chi_{22}(\underline{\eta})$ are function of the gradient of the virtual displacement field. T^{11} and T^{22} are the tensions

on the unit woven cell in warp and weft directions. M^{11} and M^{22} are the bending moments on the woven cell respectively in warp and weft directions. M^s is the in-plane shear moment. The mechanical behaviour of the textile reinforcement defines a relation between the loads $T^{\alpha\alpha}$, M^s , $M^{\alpha\alpha}$ and the strain field.

Fig.4. Rotation free three node finite element made of unit woven cells.

Experimental tests specific to textile composite reinforcements are used to obtain these mechanical properties. The biaxial tensile test gives the tensions T^{11} and T^{22} in function of the axial strain ϵ_{11} and ϵ_{22} , the picture frame or the bias extension test gives the shear moment M^s in function of the angle change γ between warp and weft yarns [13] and the bending tests give the bending moments M^{11} and M^{22} in function respectively of χ_{11} and χ_{22} [14]. The three node triangle shown figure 4 is composed of woven cells.

Fig.5. Hemispherical forming of an unbalanced fabric. Experiment and simulation.

The virtual generalized strains $\epsilon_{11}(\underline{\eta})$, $\epsilon_{22}(\underline{\eta})$, $\gamma(\underline{\eta})$, $\chi_{11}(\underline{\eta})$ and $\chi_{22}(\underline{\eta})$ can be related to the virtual nodal displacements of the nodes of the element taking into account the interpolation of the geometric and kinematic conditions within the element. Especially, using a rotation free approach [15], the curvatures $\chi_{11}(\underline{\eta})$, $\chi_{22}(\underline{\eta})$ are related to the virtual nodal displacement of the nodes 1, 2, 3 of the element and to those of the node 4, 5, 6 of the neighbouring triangles. This permits to define a shell element without rotation degrees of freedom. Using these strain interpolations in the internal virtual works defined equations 9, 10 and 11 lead to the internal nodal loads of tensions, in-plane shear and bending respectively. Details of the expressions of these nodal loads can be found in [12].

The hemispherical forming of the very unbalanced twill is simulated using the semi-discrete elements defined above. The blank holder is a 6 kg ring submitted to its own weight. This final shape is well

obtained by the simulation (figure 5). The ratio of the lengths after deformation l_{weft}/l_{warp} is equal at the top of the hemisphere to 1.8 in experiments and in simulation as well. There are many wrinkles, especially along the vertical axis. They are fairly well obtained by the simulation. Other simulations using the semi-discrete approach with comparisons with forming experiments are presented in [12, 16, 17]

5 Conclusions

The discrete approach is attractive and promising. The very specific mechanical behaviour of the textile material due to the contacts and friction between the yarns and to the change of direction is implicitly taken into account. If some sliding occurs between warp and weft yarns, they can be simulated. This is not possible by the continuous approaches that consider the textile material as a continuum. This is an important point because it can be necessary to prevent such a sliding in a process. Nevertheless, the main drawback of the discrete approach is the necessary compromise that must be done between the accuracy of the model of the unit woven cell and the total number of degrees of freedom. The modelling of the unit cell must be accurate enough to obtain a correct macroscopic mechanical behaviour, but the number of degrees of freedom of each cell must remain small in order to compute a forming process for which there will be thousand of woven cells. The continuous approach is the most commonly used in composite reinforcement forming today. The main advantage is to use standard shell or membrane finite element. The only mechanical behaviour has to be specified in order to take the very particular behaviour of textile materials into account. Many models exist, but none of them is clearly admitted. The semi-discrete approach aims to avoid the use of stress tensors and directly define the loading on a woven unit cell by the warp and weft tensions and by in-plane shear and bending moments. These quantities are simply defined on a woven unit cell and above all they are directly measured by standard tests on composite reinforcements (biaxial tension, picture frame, bias extension and bending tests).

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